

Initial Assessment of the *Metsemegologolo* Database by the AHRC/NEH Team

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Overview

The *Metsemegologolo* project began in 2020 under the direction of Stefania Merlo, Justine Winjes, and Anton Coetzee, based at University of Witwatersrand, University of Pretoria, and the KwaZulu Natal Museum (Republic of South Africa, or RSA hereafter). *Metsemegologolo*, ‘ancient towns’ in Setswana (<https://www.metsemegologolo.org.za>), is an open-source prototype database containing archaeological data, heritage objects, historical maps, oral histories and poetry about precolonial African urbanisms. The current NEH/AHRC grant focuses on how to best mobilize the *metsemegologolo* archive for digital storytelling within resource-limited educational environments.

One of the primary goals of the *metsemegologolo* database is to raise awareness of the topic of African urbanism, especially the deep-rooted nature and unique historical trajectories associated with African cities. While urban centers elsewhere are often defined by dense populations, social stratification, monumental architecture, among other traits, African urban centers, in contrast, have traditionally been characterized by high mobility, and a lack of control or dependence on central places or agriculture. In essence, African urban centers developed differently in the form and function of other early urban centers, in ways that directly play into how power operates within those societies. African urban centers in southern Africa, the immediate focus of the archive, began to coalesce approximately 1,000 years ago.

While there is merit for understanding unique pasts and upending traditional narratives, there is also practical value in studying how these places have functioned over the long term, knowing that future challenges depend on deep cultural understandings. Today, Africa has one of the fastest urban growth rates in the world: by 2050, these cities will be home to 90 million people more than presently are, with a quarter of the world’s population living in Africa more generally; by the end of this century it is estimated that the world’s biggest cities will be concentrated in Africa. Understanding long-term trajectories and historical contingencies that have influenced these places are key for effective local governmental and international policy for sustainable growth.

However, precolonial African cities—like precolonial Africa more generally—does not feature even marginally within primary and secondary education in South Africa; students are only exposed to the deep and unique roots of African urbanism at the undergraduate level, if at all (i.e., only by taking specific courses on this topic within a related major). Similar issues can be said in other African countries. Although neighboring Botswana has greater curricula emphasis on the topic of prehistory, how broadly and deeply students engage, and how the past is presented as relating to the present, remain the heart of the issue. The corresponding underdevelopment of digital educational resources magnifies the issue further. From an international perspective, many digital archives relate to the trans-Atlantic slave trade (e.g., enslaved.org, slavevoyages.org), the period after Emancipation in the United States (LiberatedAfricans.org), or 20th century liberation struggles (e.g., africanactivist.msu.edu). Exemplary efforts by the University of Cape Town, for example, with the Bleek and Lloyd Archive, the Five Hundred Years Archive, and Emandulo provide an African-centered resources. However, quality online educational resources that engage with students in-depth and across media types about precolonial African archaeology, of precolonial African cities, are extremely limited.

The *metsemegologolo* platform is organized through spatial relationships that are reflected both in the production of the metadata and in the embedding of geographic information (via registration of geographic coordinates) into the objects themselves. The environment includes an interface for a geographically based and interactive display and analysis of five interrelated components: (1) a searchable text-based database of materials relevant for sites and archaeological structures; (2) a photo and image archive; (3) an object archive; (4) a linguistic archive; (5) various Geographic Information System (GIS) layers integrating a range of historical and contemporary information. All materials will be geolocated and keyed to search terms in the database. The platform will also offer a number of curated narratives or pathways along which these materials can be explored. It will also be possible for these narratives to be supplemented, shaped or created by members of a wider audience. At present, there are two sites represented in the database: Seoke, a 18th century stonewall site located in Botswana near the South African border that was the capital of the Ngwaketse peoples; and uMgungundlovu, a 19th century military and political capital and military complex in South Africa for the Zulu.

The platform uses a flexible, extensible data framework designed around the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model, which is intended to provide for metadata and information interchange within the digital heritage realm. Deployment of CIDOC-CRM allows fine-grained recording of object metadata, and formation as well as exposition of both spatial and semantic relationships between objects within the archive. The design philosophy and implementation of the platform is aligned with current, cutting-edge practice within the fields of digital heritage and archaeology.

The customized archive is currently being populated in two modes: upload of single digital objects and creation of the metadata directly in the archival platform (this process was used for complex spatial objects such as point and line shapefiles of archaeological landscape features and 3D large objects) and bulk upload of text, image and 3D files from a Google sheet containing digital objects and their metadata. At present, the spreadsheet contains 936 different items, with 362 items ingested into the archive. The platform was extended to afford the capability to record paradata representing all steps (and associated datasets) of production of digital objects and their derivatives. Additionally, the *metsemegologolo* project is experimenting with its own Omeka Classic instance, using a format and routine for un-intermediated export of objects into Omeka for exhibitions and curations, including 3D objects and those with geospatial data.

At present, the *metsemegologolo* project anticipates challenges with 1) digital storytelling in low-resource environments, where the speed and number of computers and internet access may be varied; 2) issues related to language and accessibility of the database for its users; 3) the complexity of spatial data and spatially-organized digital archives; 4) creative ways to make meaningful and useful links to the expansive corpus of relevant materials; 5) user-driven storytelling, in contrast to prepared digital stories; 6) copyright and permissions issues from a range of institutions and countries; all while keeping in mind the 7) eventual expansion of the archive, its use and users, and its long-term sustainability.

Storytelling Topics

Early NEH-AHRC project meetings focused especially on the storytelling components (called “curations” hereafter) and for research utilization by African archaeologists, historians, and other humanists. Discussion of potential topics of interest for research and educational purposes could drive both future directions of what site or objects are prioritized, and what descriptions of the objects and connections that can be made among objects would help link them together.

For this stage of the curation development, the UK/RSA team wanted to focus broadly on a site (spatially)-based exploration of Seokwe, one of two sites that was already in the database, that incorporated a variety of media. The RSA team in particular discussed topics of interest in South Africa and Botswana that are 1) enhanced by having access to spatial data - this being a unique feature of the archive itself and 2) core to the identity of peoples.

Topics of interest presented to the group included:

- Size and layout of African urban centers
- Chieftainship
- Neighbors and Relationships among Groups
- Cattle
- Trade
- Scales of consumption and sustainability

- Landscape environment (terrain, soils, wildlife, plants, etc)
- Domination and resistance
- Splendor
- Heterogeneity and urban aggregation
- Diet
- Production
- Mining and metallurgy

From the list, cattle was chosen both because it served as a central physical and symbolic element in Tswana history and tradition, and the topic cross-cut a variety of media available in the archive. Two curations, one on the movement of Tswana groups in the 18th and 19th century and one on the history of the BaNgwaketse as presented in a 1942 journal article by Isaac Schapera were developed, with direct links in the archive and in the Omeka instance.

Storytelling Formats and Logistics

With general direction and a first theme defined, the group continued discussions about how the archive and the curations would interact with one another. Topics included evaluation of the various strengths of prepared curations, where the story is prepared beforehand, or if self-directed curations, where some or all of the story is generated by the user, would offer a better approach. With prepared curations, a guided tour through the archive would allow the user to access quality content with perhaps less apprehension of exploring new content and making the most meaningful use of the archive, at least with respect to utilizing a variety of sources and media types (provided that was a strength of the curation), or for exploring a particular topic that the user may not have otherwise considered or explored in the same way. Beyond a lower barrier to entry use, it also requires less technical skill from the user, as prepared curations do not require aggregating and linking content together. It's less time-intensive, therefore in multiple respects, further so because exploration can be the minimal time to complete a curation, while still being able to have content delivered to the users in an active, engaging manner that complements other forms of teaching. However, predetermined curations are not necessarily flexible in terms of content, and have a relatively fixed amount of time for exploration that might be too long or too short. Content may cover material that is already known, less interesting, or targeted for a different grade level. The top-down model has the potential to fall into a neocolonial trap wherein (scientific) knowledge is known and gate-kept by outside experts. The group discussed the potential for prepared curations to at least be used as examples for self-generative curations. Another middle-ground proposed by the group was the idea of prepared mini-curations, that would link together a few concepts and items that users could either learn from (those connections, relationships between various data types) or even directly build from and incorporate within their own curations. The analogy from the group was to offer a couple puzzle pieces that were already linked together to build from. Mini-curations, or even encouraging self-generated mini-curations (as opposed to fuller, long-form curations) could allow for more short-term engagements by the user and/or for narrower lesson plans where

relevant content might be far more limited in nature. It further sparked a conversation about the places in which self-directed curations could take place, such as at a museum as part of a museum tour.

With respect to connecting the archive with potential curations, the group agreed that making the best use of the archive's unique strength in spatial data, and organization around spatial relationships between objects held the greatest potential for good user engagement. Objects with some amount of spatial correlation, patterning because they had been grouped together, could lead to insights that are not discernable when considering an individual object, or by just a group of objects themselves. Spatial relationships further have the ability to explore long-term trends, as repeated use of a particular place through time may become apparent - and can be easily explored with geospatial data encoded and prioritized. The *metsemegologolo* group emphasized the need to ensure appropriate paradata and metadata are present, and even auto generated partially or completely, while conforming to FAIR principles. Additional logistics for the users were discussed, on what the permission structure should be for the use of various data and the ability to download images or models from the archives. For the latter, the group turned to experiences from the CAST group, with the Hampson Virtual Museum, where . where using documents conforms to FAIR principles. For the former, the group discussed the feasibility and use of a citable DOI for objects as they are incorporated into curations or subsequent publications by more experienced users. A recent article by Kansa and Kansa (2021) and Opitz and colleagues (2022:132-133) helped inform about infrastructures for data sharing and the importance of recognizing the digital representation of a physical object as a product with intellectual property (let alone a derivative that can and should be scrutinized). Since the collections are based in South Africa and Botswana, but the group also includes US and UK senior personnel, discussion of whose best policy practices should drive the options such as registering users, what data needs to be locationally blind, or not being able to download, etc. The group from South Africa expressed some concerns about long-term hosting strategies, as the current solution was to host in Germany (the cheapest available quality, i.e., reliable option due to a tepid response from University of Witwatersrand), especially with future hits and usage being primarily based in South Africa and Botswana. Another anticipated problem emerging from group discussions was the best ways to use and incorporate relevant objects based on association with sites in the archive. For example, one of the researchers at the KwaZulu Natal Museum was already beginning to link out to objects curated at the British Museum, pulling in object metadata and the image from the BM. Use policies vary from museum to museum, especially internationally, and although the issue would likely have to be addressed on an individual basis, a protocol should be established in the next stage before full implementation.

References

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